

An Assessment of Key Macroeconomic Variables for Forecasting Electricity Demand and Network Planning

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Abstract

This paper explores the influence of a set of macroeconomic variables on electricity demand across different voltage levels in Portugal, between 2012 and 2023, by using a hybrid forecasting framework that combines Seasonal AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average with eXogenous variables (SARIMAX) and Support Vector Machines (SVM).

In Portugal, the Transmission and Distribution System Operators to forecast electricity consumption use macroeconomic scenarios to plan and develop their networks. However, a review of the literature reveals a limited diversity of macroeconomic variables, potentially overlooking more effective proxies.

The results show that for higher voltage systems, usually associated with industrial production or other heavy intensive electricity activities, the best predictive variables are the related to investment conditions. On the other hand, for low voltage systems, typically serving residential and small commercial users, results were more diverse: Wages, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), investment and credit conditions were the variables that posed the least error in forecasting.

These findings highlight the importance of adapting forecasting models to the specific characteristics of user groups and voltage levels and provide insights for network planning, investment strategies, and tariff design, enabling the alignment of infrastructure development and pricing mechanisms with the specific needs of different consumer segments.

Keywords: electricity demand, voltage levels, income elasticity, forecasting, macroeconomics

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1. Introduction

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Accurate forecasting of electricity demand has an important role on the efficient planning and operation of energy systems. Given the recent transformations in the energy field (International Renewable Energy Agency - (IRENA, 2024) due to factors such as renewable energy integration (including hydrogen), decarbonization policies, and shifting consumption patterns (driven by, for example, self-consumption or electrification), demand forecasts that can adapt to the overall context are a useful tool. Among the various methodologies used for this purpose, hybrid models that combine statistical and machine learning techniques have demonstrated superior accuracy. As (Lee and Cho, 2022) put it "All hybrid machine learning models exhibited significantly superior predictive power compared to the time series model". In particular, the combination of Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average with exogenous variables (SARIMAX) and Support Vector Machines (SVM) has emerged as one strong approach to capture both linear and non-linear relationships in energy/electricity demand data.

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Macroeconomic variables usually considered are Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as in (Csereklyei, 2020) or industrial production indexes/gross value added (Liddle and Hasanov, 2022) typically for industrial consumption. Household available income (or wages) are considered in the domestic demand (for example in (Zhu et al., 2018) or (Pellini, 2021)). These variables have long been considered as drivers of electricity demand. However, as most papers do not provide clear information about the selection of the macroeconomic variables, the extent to which specific macroeconomic indicators enhance the accuracy of electricity demand forecasting remains an open question. This paper seeks to address this gap by identifying the best macroeconomic variable for electricity demand forecasting using a hybrid SARIMAX + SVM model.

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Electricity demand is inherently influenced by a complex combination of factors, including weather conditions, demographic trends, and economic activity (Csereklyei, 2020). Macroeconomic variables introduce a different dimension of variability, particularly over medium to long-term horizons. For example, economic growth often correlates with increased industrial production and commercial activities, leading to higher electricity consumption. Conversely, economic downturns may suppress demand as businesses scale back operations and households tighten budgets.

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An important innovation in this paper is the investigation of the relationship between macroeconomic variables and electricity demand across different voltage levels. These voltage levels correspond to distinct user profiles and consumption patterns: low voltage (LV) systems are typically associated with residential and small commercial users, medium voltage (MV) systems with larger commercial and industrial consumers, and high-voltage (HV) or very high voltage systems (VHV) with major industrial players or transmission systems. Thus, this paper offers a comprehensive understanding of the drivers of electricity demand and the most effective forecasting inputs for different segments of the energy

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system. Voltage-level analysis is crucial for network planning, investment decisions and tariff design, as it enables utilities, regulatory authorities and policymakers (Council of European Energy Regulators ((CEER, 2021) and (CEER, 2010)) to align infrastructure development and pricing strategies with the specific needs of each segment of the electricity market that supports efficient resource allocation (Esteves et al., 2015).

The key highlights of the paper are:

- **Geographical and time context:** Focus on the Portuguese electricity supplied over the power grid between 2012 and 2023.
- **Variable Selection:** Evaluation of a set of 23 macroeconomic and financial variables.
- **Model Implementation:** Development of a forecasting hybrid tool that integrates the selected macroeconomic variable as an exogenous factor. In this context, it is provided to the national regulatory authority for energy services a state-of-the-art tool that can make independent forecasts to analyze investment proposal and tariff structures.
- **Performance Evaluation:** Comparison and assessment of the impact of different specifications on key metrics such as Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD).
- **Practical Insights:** Provide actionable insights into the relationship between macroeconomic conditions and electricity demand, contributing to improved decision-making for energy policy and market operations.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature on electricity demand forecasting and the role of macroeconomic variables. Section 3 describes the data and the methodological framework, including the information about the macroeconomic variables selected, as well as the SARIMAX + SVM hybrid model. Section 4 presents the results of the forecasting experiments, highlighting the performance of different variables. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper, summarizing the key contributions and identifying areas for future research.

2. Literature Review

On this chapter it will be presented the relevant literature review regarding the use of macroeconomic variables as determinants or predictors of electricity demand.

The income elascity

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Table 1 presents a summary of recent studies conducted to assess the income elasticity of electricity demand. Furthermore, the key information is to identify which macroeconomic variables are the most common to represent income.

Table 1: Summary of Studies on Income Variables and User Types

Authors	Data	Region	Method	Variable for Income	User Type
(İsmail Kavaz, 2025)	1980-2018	Turkey	STSM	Household Expenditure	Household
(Nna et al., 2025)	1975-2022	Cameroon	MLR	GDP/Income per capita	(Non)Household
(Carrasco-Gutierrez and Ehrl, 2023)	2003–2015	Brazil	VECM	Household Income	Household
(Xue et al., 2023)	1994-2022	12 EU countries	ECM	GDP per capita	Household
(Tran et al., 2023)	1981-2020	India	ARDL	GDP/GVA	(Non)Household
(Mikayilov et al., 2023)	1990-2019	Saudi Arabia	STSM	GVA	Non-Household
(Kostakis and Lolos, 2022)	2009–2018	Greece	PPM	Household Income	Household
(Li et al., 2022)	2006–2016	China	AIDS	Household Expenditure	Household
(de Souza et al., 2022)	1974–2016	Brazil	ARDL	GDP	Household
(Romero-Jordán and del Río, 2022)	2006-2012	Spain	IV-SFA	Household Expenditure	Household
(Liddle and Hasanov, 2022)	1978–2016	OECD	DP	Industrial Value Added	Non-household
(Bohlmann and Inglesi-Lotz, 2021)	1975–2016	South Africa	ARDL	GNDI	Household
(Othman and Hariri, 2021)	1980–2020	Malaysia	ARDL	GDP per capita	Household
(Pellini, 2021)	1975–2018	12 EU countries	ECM	GDP per capita	Household
(Jia et al., 2021)	2014	China	IV	Household Income	Household
(Liddle and Huntington, 2021)	1978–2013	55 countries	DP	GDP per capita	Household
(Martins et al., 2021)	2004–2011	Brazil	ECM	Wages per worker	Household
(Kostakis, 2020)	2017	Greece	QR	Household Income	Household
(Alfalah et al., 2020)	1972-2017	Kuwait	ECM	Household Expenditure	Household
(Cserekyei, 2020)	1996–2016	EU	DP	GDP	(Non)Household
(Cialani and Mortazavi, 2018)	1995–2015	EU	DP	GDP	(Non)Household
(Burke and Abayasekara, 2018)	2013–2015	USA States	DP	GDP per capita	Total
(Wang and Mogi, 2017)	1989-2014	Japan	TVP	Real income	Total

Note: AIDS: - Almost Ideal Demand System; ARDL: Autoregressive Distributed Lags; DP - Dynamic Partial Adjustment Model; ECM - Error Correction Model; MLR - Multiple Linear Regression; QR - Quantile Regression; IV - Instrumental Variables Model; PPM - Pseudo Panel Model; SFA - Stochastic Frontier Analysis; STSM - Structural Time Series Modelling; TVP - Time Varying Parameters; VECM - Vector Error Correction Model; GNDI - Gross National Disposable Income; GVA - Gross Value Added;

It can be observed that the most common user types analyzed are the residential consumers, for which the most common variable is available household income with GDP also appearing in a substantial number of studies.

Regarding non-household consumers, GDP and gross value added (GVA) are the common variables identified.

It is interesting to notice, as a side quest, that in these studies, the long-run income elasticity varies between 0.04 (Alfalah et al., 2020) to 1.59 (Jia et al., 2021) with the short-run elasticities having a more restrict interval.

Though there are some variation in the indicators used to measure income, there is a clear strong concentration around the GDP and household available income or expenditure. These measures broadly capture the economic activity and purchasing power that drive electricity consumption.

Regarding the methodology in this paper it used a forecasting approach rather than a methodology to estimate elasticities. Most of the research on predicting electricity consumption rely mostly on univariate machine learning, time series or hybrid algorithms that do not incorporate exogenous variables (Fan et al., 2020a), (Fan et al., 2020b),

(Elsaraiti et al., 2021), (Parreño, 2022). 121

However, the hypothesis to be tested in this paper is that other macroeconomic and 122
financial variables, such as investment or employment levels, can also have a direct or 123
indirect link to income and could significantly influence electricity demand. For instance, 124
investment in industries or infrastructure may spur electricity usage in the industrial sec- 125
tor, while financial measures like credit availability or stock market performance might 126
better capture income dynamics in certain contexts. These alternative indicators may 127
provide more sector-specific insights or reflect changes in economic conditions that GDP 128
may overlook. Exploring these measures could improve the accuracy and relevance of 129
electricity demand forecasts, particularly in rapidly evolving or structurally distinct eco- 130
nomies. 131

The portuguese context 132

The EU Directive 2019/944 (EuropeanParliament, 2019) requires electricity distribu- 133
tion system operators (DSOs) to develop and publish Distribution Network Development 134
Plans (DNDPs) aimed at integrating renewable energy, facilitating storage solutions, sup- 135
porting transport electrification, and informing users about network expansions. The 136
(CEER, 2021) emphasizes that these plans must account for factors such as electrification, 137
energy storage, and distributed energy resources. In Portugal, Directive (EU) 2019/944 138
was transposed into Decree-Law 15/2022 (NationalParliament, 2022), mandating that 139
both transmission and distribution system operators conduct macroeconomic analyses 140
and long-term forecasts to identify future investment requirements. In this context it is 141
important to keep in mind that electricity transmission and distribution are activities 142
characterized by natural monopolies and are managed by firms operating under a conces- 143
sion regime (Priest, 1993). Their operators are required to submit investment plans to 144
the national regulatory authority for review and approval by the national parliament. 145

Understanding the analytical models employed by these firms, particularly their meth- 146
ods for assessing the relationship between income and electricity demand, is essential for 147
evaluating their investment proposals. 148

The Portuguese Transmission System Operator (TSO) performs comprehensive ana- 149
lyses of total electricity consumption ((REN, 2024)). The diagram below highlights the 150
primary drivers influencing electricity demand forecasts, with the developed scenarios 151
reflecting a blend of various perspectives on the evolution of these drivers. 152

Figure 1: Drivers of electricity consumption according to the national TSO

Source: REN

According to Redes Energéticas Nacionais (REN), forecasting electricity consumption 153
 is a complex task influenced by multiple economic, social, technological, environmental 154
 and political factors that often send conflicting signals. To deal with this complexity, the 155
 TSO constructs a series of contrasting scenarios that control for potential challenges. 156

Within the general EU's vision of decarbonization, this includes accelerating the elec- 157
 trification of energy consumption, promoting energy efficiency and introducing renewable 158
 and low-carbon fuels such as hydrogen, especially in hard-to-decarbonize sectors. Por- 159
 tugal's commitment to carbon neutrality by 2050, outlined in the Roadmap to Carbon 160
 Neutrality (GovernmentOfPortugal, 2019) and the National Energy and Climate Plan 161
 2030 (Directorate-General for Energy and Geology (DGEG, 2023)), underpins its efforts 162
 to align energy demand with decarbonization goals. 163

As for the comparison with Spain, the TSO highlights that Portugal's electricity con- 164
 sumption intensity relative to GDP has been higher since 2009, while its per capita con- 165
 sumption remains lower though is catching up: In 2000, Portugal's per capita consumption 166
 was 75% of Spain's, but by 2022, it was 94%. 167

In this context, the TSO has developed four electricity demand scenarios (in the ten 168
 year development and investment network proposal plan) based on two axes: "speed of 169
 decarbonization" and "economic growth". These scenarios consider different perspectives 170
 of economic growth: an upper scenario with favorable growth conditions, a middle scenario 171
 with moderate growth and a lower scenario with less favourable growth. The Economic 172
 Growth axis assesses the varying degrees of European energy policy integration, the uptake 173
 of electric vehicles, the development of decentralized generation and the impact of financial 174
 incentives. European funding, innovation and research are also key drivers of economic 175
 growth and project development. 176

The TSO uses a monthly structural model to forecast electricity consumption, integ- 177
 rating explanatory variables such as calendar effects, weather conditions and economic 178

activity. These models decompose variables into components such as trend, seasonality and cycle, using adaptive methods such as the Kalman filter for recursive estimation.

REN concludes that economic variables have played a decreasing role in explaining electricity demand, particularly since 2009. The elasticity of electricity demand to GDP in Portugal seems to be falling significantly, indicating that factors such as energy efficiency play a crucial role.

Furthermore, in the residential sector, the explanatory coefficient of economic variables has consistently decreased. In the tertiary sector, this downward trend began in 2013, while in the industrial sector the coefficient stagnated after 2007, followed by sporadic fluctuations. Nevertheless, the TSO considers that macroeconomic development scenarios remain crucial for scenario building, even though energy efficiency is increasingly influencing demand. The TSO underlines the importance of integrating the impact of energy efficiency, recognizing its growing importance in all sectors.

As for the distribution level, the main Portuguese Distribution System Operator (DSO) (serving 95% of clients) applies a hybrid model (E-Redes, 2022) combining multiple linear regression with neural networks. Consumption forecasts for the demand directed at the Distribution Network are broken down by segment - VHV, HV, MV, SLV, NLV and PI. The model accounts for macroeconomic effects, temperature, calendar effects, consumption inertia, energy efficiency, electric vehicle consumption, and self-consumption. It turns out that electricity consumption behaviour for VHV, HV, MV and SLV segments proved to be sensitive to economic activity, as measured by GDP. On the other hand, NLV was statistically significant when related to private consumption. The DSO analyzes annual data over the period between 1994 and 2023 to make it possible to assess this relationship. For projections and in order to assess the annual rates of change to be used, the most current macroeconomic projections at the time are analyzed.

The regression coefficients of the DSO analysis are presented in the table 2 :

Table 2: GDP and Private Consumption coefficients

	Gross Domestic Product	Private Consumption
VHV	0.005	-
HV	0.011	-
MV	0.029	-
SLV	0.008	-
NLV	-	0.117

As for the inland Azores DSO, it uses a combination of autoregressive, linear, and exponential models for forecasting, supplemented by estimates of exogenous factors like tourism and construction. Madeira DSO (also inland)bases its forecasts on recent data and economic activity, particularly in tourism.

In summary, national DSO's and TSO use macroeconomic variables to predict economic forecasts, even though there is some evidence that this relationship may be declining over time due to energy efficiency measures and self-consumption. Several economic in-

dicators are used, namely GDP, gross value added and private consumption, as well as other sector specific variables (related, for example, to the development of tourism). It should also be highlighted that the income elasticities, vary between 0 and 0.25, which are small compared to the interval given in the literature review. Now that it is established that Portuguese utilities and decision makers look at future income development of the macroeconomic conditions, then it makes sense to provide an analysis that can identify the best macroeconomic and financial variables to follow (projections availability is also a concern).

3. Data and Methods

3.1 Data

Table 3 provides a brief qualitative description of the variables collected and respective characteristics.

Table 3: Macroeconomic Variables and Characteristics

Variable	Description	Frequency	Expected Impact	Source
GDP	Gross domestic product	Quarterly	+	INE
INV	Gross fixed capital formation	Quarterly	+	INE
PC	Private consumption	Quarterly	+	INE
IEB	Balance of goods and services	Quarterly	+/-	INE
NFA	Net financial assets	Quarterly	+	BdP
FDI	Foreign direct investment	Quarterly	+	BdP
ER	Employment rate	Monthly	+	INE
UR	Unemployment rate	Monthly	+	INE
IPI	Industrial production index	Monthly	+	BdP
ESI	Economic sentiment index	Monthly	+	BdP
CCI	Consumer confidence index	Monthly	+	BdP
ICI	Industry confidence index	Monthly	+	BdP
PS	Private savings	Quarterly	+	BdP
PAI	Private available income	Quarterly	+	BdP
W	Wages	Monthly	+	BdP/INE
PD	Public Debt	Monthly	-	BdP
PSI20	Portuguese Stock Index	Monthly	+	Bloomberg
ESTXX	European Stock Index	Monthly	+	Bloomberg
OT10	Treasury bonds 10 years	Monthly	-	BdP
OT2	Treasury bonds 2 years	Monthly	-	BdP
E6M	Euribor 6 months	Monthly	-	Bloomberg
CRED	Loans to non-financial corps	Monthly	+	BdP
TXCRED	Interest rate of CRED	Monthly	-	BdP

Note: INE - National Statistics Institution ; BdP - Central Bank of the Portuguese Republic

Additionally, Table 4 shows the summary statistics for monthly electricity consumption supplied to customers at a given voltage. It should be noted that the consumption used to set tariffs is the top-bottom cumulative network demand(excluding self-consumption). Tariffs are regulated prices, that reflect the costs of regulated activities and for which the national regulatory authority defines the amount of allowed revenue. Network access tariffs are passed on in the bills of all consumers, both in the regulated and liberalized markets, and usually are set given a combination of drivers (energy or capacity).

Table 4: Table of Energy Values (Transposed)

Category	Min	Mean	Max	SD	Unit
VHV	99 366	185 040	232 200	22 364	MWh
HV	243 444	563 867	769 880	43 674	MWh
MV	909 815	1 200 726	1 381 002	74 846	MWh
SLV	168 863	269 398	311 660	22 196	MWh
NLV	1 253 620	1 418 280	1 944 057	140 839	MWh
NLV3	99 327	155 924	218 105	15 096	MWh
NLV2	154 610	198 863	246 926	15 640	MWh
NLV1	902 396	1 063 493	1 576 580	133 852	MWh
PI	53 621	101 793	148 567	21 356	MWh
Total	3 073 474	3 637 312	4 168 575	168 767	MWh

Note: VHV - Very High Voltage (voltage between phases whose effective value is greater than 110 kV); HV - High Voltage (voltage between phases whose effective value is greater than 45 kV and equal to or less than 110 kV); SLV - Special Low Voltage dedicated to firms (low voltage with contracted power greater than 41.4 kV); NLV - Normal Low Voltage (low voltage with contracted power less than or equal to 41.4 kV); NLV1 - Normal Low Voltage with contracted power less or equal than 13.8 kV; NLV2 -Normal Low Voltage with contracted power between 13.8 kV and 20.7 kV; NLV3 - Normal Low Voltage with contracted power between 20.7 kV and 41.4kV; MV - Medium Voltage (voltage between phases whose effective value is greater than 1 kV and equal to or less than 45 kV).

Additionally, to control for other drivers it was also included weather conditions (Heating degrees days), electricity prices per voltage levels and number of consumers with active contracts.

3.2 Methods

SARIMAX model

The ARIMA models, developed by Box and Jenkins, are powerful and useful forecasting techniques for forecasting time series. In essence, ARIMA models estimate future values of the time series as a linear combination of historical and residual data. There are three components in such a model: the differentiation order for seasonality, the autoregressive and moving average orders.

The SARIMAX model is an extension of the ARIMA model that accounts for seasonality and exogenous variables in time series forecasting. It incorporates seasonal autoregressive (SAR) and seasonal moving average (SMA) components alongside the regular autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA) components.

The advantage of using ARIMA models is their versatility and the fact that they can be adjusted to predict different temporal phenomena ((Box et al., 2015)). Since ARIMA is a linear model, it cannot capture non-linear patterns in a time series; therefore, different predictive models based on machine learning and deep learning techniques have been used in time series forecasting to predict non-linear fluctuations.

SARIMAX is defined as:

$$\phi(B)\Phi(B^s)(1 - B)^d y_t = c + \theta(B)\Theta(B^s)\epsilon_t + \mathbf{X}_t\boldsymbol{\beta} \quad (1)$$

where:

- $\phi(B)$ is the autoregressive polynomial of order p , - $\Phi(B^s)$ is the seasonal autoregressive polynomial of order P , - $\theta(B)$ is the moving average polynomial of order q , - $\Theta(B^s)$ is the seasonal moving average polynomial of order Q , - $(1 - B)^d$ is the differencing operator for non-stationarity, - c is the constant (intercept), - \mathbf{X}_t is the vector of exogenous variables at time t , - $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the vector of coefficients for the exogenous variables, - ϵ_t is the white noise error term.

The SARIMAX model combines the non-seasonal ARMA terms with seasonal ARMA terms, and it can include exogenous variables to capture external influences. The backward shift operator B is used for lagged values of the series, while B^s is used for seasonal lags with period s .

The seasonal autoregressive terms $\Phi(B^s)$ and moving average terms $\Theta(B^s)$ are of key importance when modeling data with periodic behavior, such as monthly data available for this paper. The SARIMAX model, therefore, allows for better modeling of seasonal and non-stationary data compared to the standard ARIMA model.

In the SARIMAX model, exogenous variables \mathbf{X}_t are included to account for external factors that influence the time series. These variables are assumed to have a linear relationship with the dependent variable y_t , and their coefficients are estimated along with the AR and MA terms. In this paper the exogenous variables will be heating degree days, electricity prices, number of customers and one single macroeconomic variable per run.

This model is particularly useful when there are additional inputs that impact the forecast, such as economic indicators, weather conditions, prices or other factors. Additionally it allows to get short-run elasticities.

The parameters of the SARIMAX model are typically estimated using the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) method, which finds the values of $\phi(B)$, $\Phi(B^s)$, $\theta(B)$, $\Theta(B^s)$, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, and c that maximize the likelihood function given the observed data. Evaluative metrics such as the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) are used to select the optimal model.

The model for SARIMAX was chosen with the function "auto.arima" from the R package "forecast". This package evaluates models based on information criteria like AIC, Corrected AIC (AICc) (penalizes model complexity while rewarding better fit) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), similar to AIC but penalizes complexity more heavily. If seasonality is suspected (based on the periodicity of the data), "auto.arima" includes seasonal ARIMA in the search ((Hyndman and Khandakar, 2008) and (Wang et al., 2006))

Support Vector Regression model

SVR was chosen because it can handle limited number of observations (only the support vectors, ie. a subset of training data are used to define the decision boundary, making SVR efficient in memory usage) compared to other machine learning methods that need a high number of observations. Additionally, it is combined in several studies together with the ARIMA approach ((Rubio and Alba, 2022) and (Kao et al., 2020)), that demonstrate the capacity to improve forecasts accuracy upon the ARIMA models. Lastly, it is robust to outliers, since its algorithm focuses on minimizing error within a margin of tolerance.

This machine learning algorithm is used for nonlinear regression problems as SVR uses a linear function hypothesis space in a high-dimensional feature space to be trained according to the principle of structural risk minimization. SVR inputs are mapped into a high-dimensional feature space by using a non-linear function.(Chang and Lin, 2011). The decision function for the SVR model (adopted (Rubio and Alba, 2022) math notation) can be expressed as:

$$y = w \cdot \varphi(x) + b, \quad (3)$$

where x is the input, w is the weight vector and b is the bias (both are constant vectors), and $\varphi(x)$ is a nonlinear function. The principal objective of SVR algorithms is to find the best parameters w, b in Equation (3), to solve an optimization problem described as follows

$$\min \left(\frac{1}{2} w^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n (\zeta_i + \zeta_i^*) \right)$$

subject to:

$$y_i - (w \cdot \varphi(x_i) + b) \leq \epsilon + \zeta_i, \quad (w \cdot \varphi(x_i) + b) - y_i \leq \epsilon + \zeta_i^*$$

$$\zeta_i, \zeta_i^* \geq 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

where ζ_i and ζ_i^* are slack variables that measure the training errors above and below an ϵ -tube, and C is a positive constant penalty coefficient that determines the degree of penalized loss when a training error occurs. The nonlinear SVR can also be expressed as a dual pattern using the Lagrange multipliers after minimizing equation. Then, the dual

optimization problem of nonlinear SVR changes to the following 310

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*)(\alpha_j - \alpha_j^*)K + \epsilon \sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) - \sum_{i=1}^n y_i(\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) \quad (5)$$

with constraints 311

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) = 0, \quad 0 \leq \alpha_i, \alpha_i^* \leq C, \quad i = 1, \dots, n,$$

where ζ_i and ζ_i^* are Lagrange multipliers with a K radial kernel function given by: 312

$$K(i, j) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x_i - x_j\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$$

. Lastly, the nonlinear (SVR) decision function can be stated as 313

$$f(x_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*)K(x_i, x_k) + b. \quad (6)$$

In order to solve the minimization problem, there are three hyperparameters to be 314
tuned, namely: 315

- **C** (Regularization parameter): Controls the trade-off between achieving a low train- 316
ing error and a low model complexity. 317
- ϵ : Hyperparameter that specifies the margin of tolerance where no penalty is given 318
for errors. 319
- σ : Regulates the impact of a single point on the decision boundary. 320

For the tuning of these hyperparamters it was used grid search i.e, a systematic ap- 321
proach that involves searching through a specified interval of hyperparameters to find the 322
combination that yields the best model performance based on the mean squared error. 323

Hybrid model 324

SARIMAX model extracts linear components and predicts them; residuals, being non- 325
linear data subcomponents, are then fit by the SVR model. The hybrid model H_t is, then, 326
expressed as 327

$$H_t = L_t + N_t, \quad (7)$$

where L_t and N_t represent the linear and non-linear components for the hybrid tech- 328
nique and are calculated based on the original time series. Let \hat{L}_t be prediction resulting 329
from the use of the SARIMAX model in the original dataset at time t ; then, the residual 330
 ϵ_t , defined as 331

$$\epsilon_t = H_t - \hat{L}_t, \quad (8)$$

is adjusted using the SVR model and can be expressed as

$$\epsilon_t = F_{SVR}(\epsilon_{t-1}, \epsilon_{t-2}, \dots, \epsilon_{t-n}) + \Delta_t, \quad (9)$$

where F_{SVR} is a nonlinear expression related to the SVR model and Δ_t is the random error.

Thus, a hybrid model can be expressed as

$$\hat{H}_t = \hat{L}_t + \hat{N}_t, \quad (10)$$

where \hat{L}_t and \hat{N}_t are the forecast values for linearity and non-linearity using the SAR-IMAX and SVR models, respectively.

The choice of this model allow us to maintain model the potential seasonality of the electricity consumption, to keep the interpretability of the SARIMAX coefficients and to further introduce non-linear relationships between variables. Additionally the use of the hybrid method is also justified by the fact that SARIMAX residuals were not normal given the results Shapiro-Wilk test of normality extended to large samples (Royston, 1982) that rejected the null hypothesis of normality in most models. As for the Ljung-box test (Box and Pierce, 1970), the results pointed to not reject the null hypothesis of independence in a given time series in most models.

Performance metrics

In order to assess the accuracy of the predictions, it is presented three common performance metrics.

First, the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), that measures the average percentage error between actual and predicted values, expressed as a percentage. This metric allows making comparisons across different variables that may be expressed in different scales.

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \times 100$$

It was also calculated the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE): Calculates the square root of the average squared differences between actual and predicted values, emphasizing larger errors. It is sensitive to the scale used.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}$$

Finally, it is presented the Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD): Represents the aver-

age absolute difference between actual and predicted values, providing a straightforward 357
measure of prediction accuracy. As RMSE it is sensitive to the scale used. 358

$$\text{MAD} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|$$

In addition to the performance metrics, a chart will be presented for each voltage 359
level on the results chapter, displaying both the out-of-sample forecasts and the actual 360
electricity demand values. The three metrics may not always align in terms of the mac- 361
roeconomic variable that results in the lowest error. When multiple variables minimize 362
these metrics, the MAPE will be prioritized for display in the chart. 363

Other transformations and particularities 364

Due to some characteristics in the data, next, it is described a series data transform- 365
ations and assumptions that were made before running the models. 366

All variables expressed in monetary terms were deflated using the Consumer's Index 367
Price with reference to 2021. Logarithmisation was performed before the variables got 368
into the "auto.arima" procedure. 369

Data was split using 75% for training (T=108) and 25% for out-of-the sample accuracy 370
determination (T=36). 371

Quarterly data series were transformed to monthly series using the Chow-Lin method- 372
ology from the "tempdisagg" R package. This method converts low-frequency data into 373
high-frequency data while ensuring consistency with the original aggregates. It relies on 374
a regression model to establish a relationship between the low-frequency target variable 375
and one or more high-frequency indicator variables (Sax and Steiner, 2013) and (Chow 376
and Lin, 1971). Even though this approach introduces some uncertainty in the data, due 377
to low level of observations (T=144), this was deemed the most adequate strategy. 378

This exercise is not a fully out-of-the sample forecasting experiment: as it is used 379
the actual values for exogenous variables, it is expected very high accuracy, in order 380
to evaluate the variation of accuracy that comes from only rotating the macroeconomic 381
variable used. 382

4. Results 383

The results section is separated by voltage level. For each subsection it is presented the 384
accuracy for each macroeconomic variable, highlighting the three best predictors. Finally 385
it is presented the actual vs foretasted values for the variable that yield the most accurate 386
predictions. 387

According to the results of SARIMAX model and table 5, at the VHV level if the bond yields at 2 years maturity have an raises by 1% then electricity demand drops 0.0052% (Additionally, the standard error is 0.0058). It should be noted that this is the coefficient associated with the SARIMAX model only. More complex relationships between the variables can be evaluated when it is further regressed residuals on a support vector regression framework.

Table 5: Performance Metrics for Models

Variable	MAPE (%)	RMSE (MWh)	MAD (MWh)
GDP	3.960	25185.266	7582.343
INV	1.946	15108.064	3504.382
PC	2.744	19826.949	5075.143
IEB	0.633	4631.851	1137.791
NFA	0.903	6884.919	1613.869
FDI	0.355	2540.640	633.760
ER	1.619	13474.446	2890.161
UR	0.935	6896.212	1691.811
IPI	0.935	7552.363	1681.949
ESI	1.309	8191.079	2465.402
CCI	0.575	2624.736	1068.905
ICI	0.646	3736.524	1232.453
PS	1.180	10006.199	2103.046
PAI	1.193	9099.405	2150.386
W	1.306	11292.239	2325.942
PD	93.957	270815.065	181704.618
PSI20	0.638	4576.026	1158.954
ESTXX	2.383	14216.702	4535.484
OT10	0.483	2953.842	850.456
OT2	0.284	1023.030	552.892
E6M	13.724	47502.172	27117.086
CRED	1.231	8034.500	2503.850
TXCRED	10.201	41236.421	20500.062

Note: Highlighted values represent the three lowest values in each column.

An hypothetical theory behind these results may suggest that a 2-year treasury bond yields serve as a determinant of VHV electricity consumption as they reflect mid-term economic outlooks and borrowing costs, influencing industrial production and energy-intensive activities that drive demand. Overall it indicates that the investment and economic conditions influence the consumption of very large consumers whose are connected to very high voltage networks (ERSE, 2024a). According to our data there is only 65 large firms with active contracts on VHV, nevertheless they consume around 5% of total electricity supplied by the network. In this context (Cremers et al., 2021) has shown that treasury yields have the ability to predict the growth rate and volatility of industrial

output. 404

Given that it is only used real values and the only variation, between models, is on 405
the macroeconomic variable used, is safe to assume that differences derive only from the 406
variable rotation. 407

Figure 2 shows very low differences between actual and forecasted values. The use of 408
exogenous real values greatly increase the accuracy as expected. 409

Figure 2: Actual and forecast electricity demand for VHV using OT2

HV 410

As for the HV segment and according to the SARIMAX model (and table 6), an 411
increase of 1% in the foreign direct investment leads to an increase on the electricity 412
demand of 0.2227% (Additionally, the standard error is 0.1609). On the SARIMAX 413
model, FDI is not significant at a 5% level. 414

Table 6: Performance Metrics for Models

Variable	MAPE (%)	RMSE (MWh)	MAD (MWh)
GDP	7.032	76712.303	39014.604
INV	4.024	50247.671	22300.720
PC	1.898	23723.556	10474.780
IEB	0.366	4710.908	2028.375
NFA	0.662	10457.339	3982.525
FDI	0.194	2203.598	1084.358
ER	1.132	15256.519	6347.093
UR	1.270	16760.639	7494.020
IPI	4.429	43534.211	24993.038
ESI	1.033	12949.433	5947.097
CCI	0.420	4990.162	2326.870
ICI	0.524	7104.732	3034.400
PS	3.890	39278.849	21206.836
PAI	0.796	10097.041	4379.926
W	0.639	9104.606	3473.393
PD	1.376	18708.514	7451.871
PSI20	0.848	12547.330	4568.710
ESTXX	0.357	4562.974	1958.730
OT10	0.613	8406.484	3336.584
OT2	0.594	8241.288	3225.586
E6M	6.423	66683.454	35103.325
CRED	2.615	30435.810	15409.259
TXCRED	0.365	6196.117	2179.168

Note: Highlighted values represent the three lowest values in each column.

Even though the FDI can be definitely be a driver of the industrial output, in particular 415 on the automotive and electronics segment (Kalotay, 2010) and (Zhou, 2024), and even 416 important (Barrios et al., 2002) for the convergence with the EU of structure and income 417 in countries like Portugal, there has been taking place a tertiarization of the Portuguese 418 economy in the last decades. Whereas the national industry is characterized by low and 419 medium-low technology products, although there has already been an evolution over the 420 last 20 years towards products with a higher technological content (BdP, 2009) 421

Figure 3 once again shows very low differences between actual and forecasted values. 422

Figure 3: Actual and forecast electricity demand for HV using FDI

MV

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At the MV level SARIMAX model points that an increase of 1% in the imports to 424
exports balance (see table 7) there is an increase on the electricity demand of 0.0631% 425
(Additionally, the standard error is 0.0153). On the SARIMAX model, the balance of 426
goods and services is significant at a 5% level. 427

Table 7: Performance Metrics for Hybrid Models

Variable	MAPE (%)	RMSE (MWh)	MAD (MWh)
GDP	0.069	1304.481	825.119
INV	0.138	5588.919	1694.871
PC	0.071	1561.107	844.047
IEB	0.027	404.634	332.626
NFA	2.448	68967.396	31033.424
FDI	0.039	779.521	465.564
ER	0.104	5766.697	1330.559
UR	0.039	645.370	465.686
IPI	0.049	1285.748	561.380
ESI	0.130	6229.691	1612.986
CCI	0.040	673.845	480.516
ICI	0.603	22457.122	7554.015
PS	0.279	11423.686	3328.047
PAI	0.036	616.463	449.064
W	0.055	1056.013	644.041
PD	3.108	80700.009	39342.007
PSI20	0.033	443.679	404.933
ESTXX	0.065	1357.729	773.011
OT10	0.040	777.228	469.436
OT2	0.043	817.825	505.342
E6M	6.516	143992.577	81175.440
CRED	0.318	12476.114	4061.956
TXCRED	3.811	98987.094	47669.172

Note: Highlighted values represent the lowest MAPE, RMSE, and MAD for each variable.

At the MV level the results also point to another macroeconomic factor that relates with investment and industrial output: The differential between imports and exports. In this context, the increase of imports to exports can often indicate more domestic activity in processing, distribution, and retail, which can be energy-intensive.

According to the Figure 4 there is some clear seasonality in the data, that was only slightly disrupted by pandemic crisis of COVID-19.

Figure 4: Actual and forecast electricity demand for MV using IEB

SLV

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Even though low voltage levels are usually associated with residential consumers, the 435
SLV is a special low voltage tariff option for small businesses that don't require high 436
installed power capacity (ERSE, 2024b). 437

Thus, for the SARIMAX model an increase of 1% in the imports to exports balance 438
(Table 8) there is an increase on the electricity demand of 0.1149% (Additionally, the 439
standard error is 0.0390). On the SARIMAX model, the balance of goods and services is 440
significant at a 5% level. 441

Table 8: Performance Metrics for Hybrid Models

Variable	MAPE (%)	RMSE (MWh)	MAD (MWh)
GDP	0.173	1312.6462	367.8743
INV	1.486	13052.7248	3555.6131
PC	0.199	1617.2570	428.1709
IEB	0.097	437.4978	228.8269
NFA	2.673	15488.2143	6944.7166
FDI	2.145	13472.1193	4843.4698
ER	2.752	17847.6548	7720.6189
UR	0.961	6621.9877	1995.4827
IPI	2.497	17513.6159	5118.8040
ESI	1.472	9104.4226	3456.1221
CCI	1.084	7401.8121	2254.7782
ICI	1.713	11072.4444	4154.2048
PS	0.184	1164.5581	400.2178
PAI	3.659	23552.1041	10061.5401
W	1.113	6762.3207	2486.7453
PD	21.025	67870.8899	56718.0130
PSI20	1.216	8220.4076	2536.0309
ESTXX	1.307	8422.7306	2786.6660
OT10	1.027	7086.3377	2128.2300
OT2	1.135	7709.2458	2360.9525
E6M	1.293	8174.2040	2811.7650
CRED	1.084	7367.9147	2250.2569
TXCRED	2.412	13042.8991	5793.1005

Note: Highlighted values represent the 3 lowest MAPE, RMSE, and MAD values for the hybrid models.

Similarly to the MV level, the IEB variable is best macroeconomic predictor the elec- 442
tricity consumption time series. Nevertheless, at this point results start to show other 443
variables like private consumption and savings as possible candidates close to the results 444
provided by the IEB variable. 445

From the figure 5 it can be observed that electricity consumption is highly seasonal 446
without a clear trend. Nevertheless, the COVID-19 broke down the patterns in 2020 and 447
2021 (large decreases in electricity consumption have also been reported by (Cerqueira 448
and da Silva, 2023) and (Santiago et al., 2021)) for Portugal and Spain. After 2022, 449
electricity demand returns to normal levels. 450

Figure 5: Actual and forecast electricity demand for SLV using IEB

NLV

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We now enter the terrain where most consumers are domestic users. First the analysis 452
of the results will focus on the whole group. Furthermore, the NLV level will be broken 453
down by power capacities. 454

The SARIMAX model results indicate that for an increase of 1% in gross domestic 455
product (Table 9) there is a decrease on the electricity demand of 0.2089% (Additionally, 456
the standard error is 0.1222). On the SARIMAX model, the GDP is not significant at a 457
5% level. 458

Table 9: Performance Metrics for Hybrid Models

Variable	MAPE (%)	RMSE (MWh)	MAD (MWh)
GDP	0.1866	14919.72	3413.16
INV	0.4903	42770.47	8894.66
PC	0.2202	17495.21	4081.66
IEB	0.6218	45175.17	11657.77
NFA	0.5261	36677.20	8753.04
FDI	1.0418	69269.74	19480.06
ER	0.4947	40263.89	9147.54
UR	1.1406	47659.06	15806.50
IPI	0.5750	47947.74	10893.18
ESI	0.5061	44200.44	9579.99
CCI	0.8755	57555.98	16386.15
ICI	0.5025	44304.78	9514.72
PS	1.2236	73033.94	22225.45
PAI	0.4054	40588.64	7619.04
W	0.6486	45493.61	11989.37
PD	33.4952	571947.69	499602.88
PSI20	0.4295	31788.64	7324.99
ESTXX	1.0356	72424.93	19314.33
OT10	0.7111	63224.26	13185.75
OT2	0.3944	31650.79	7138.52
E6M	9.7492	242671.17	138681.10
CRED	0.6651	37919.02	10633.67
TXCRED	3.0916	108901.16	44333.02

Note: Highlighted values represent the 3 lowest MAPE, RMSE, and MAD values for the hybrid models.

It should be noted that although the income elasticity of the SARIMAX model is negative (something very unusual in the given literature), coefficients can sometimes be non-significant (which can also be an effect exacerbated by falling elasticities). Additionally, the results are fine-tuned with the SVR approach, indicating that GDP may have strong non-linearities relationship with electricity consumption.

Figure 6 shows that this segment was the least affected by pandemics, registering a slight increase during lockdown periods. Other than, the series has a clear seasonal pattern without signs of an increasing trend.

Figure 6: Actual and forecast electricity demand for NLV using GDP

NLV1

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For NLV1 it can be assumed that most of the residential consumers on this level 468
 have higher income/expenditure levels, higher electrification rates (for example, they own 469
 electric vehicles), high house areas and/or a large number of persons under the household. 470

An increase of 1% in the Wages (Table 10) there is an increase on the electricity demand 471
 of 0.5004% (Additionally, the standard error is 0.0975). On the SARIMAX model, wages 472
 is significant at a 5% level. 473

Table 10: Performance Metrics for Hybrid Models

Variable	MAPE (%)	RMSE (MWh)	MAD (MWh)
GDP	1.3138	69340.91	19666.03
INV	0.8753	59704.75	12434.41
PC	1.4260	71937.69	21230.25
IEB	1.5101	75790.16	22388.65
NFA	1.0888	60257.56	14361.23
FDI	0.9822	65431.85	14772.82
ER	0.7230	45734.05	10174.87
IPI	0.7818	58336.40	11581.39
ESI	0.8158	56784.73	11964.08
CCI	1.4045	74177.47	21072.87
ICI	0.8077	56839.69	11824.92
PS	2.2494	90517.16	31156.01
PAI	1.0197	64164.28	15275.19
W	0.0866	2668.50	1103.27
PD	25.0482	343803.51	289266.19
PSI20	0.7941	60383.45	11928.79
ESTXX	1.1920	69542.31	18050.27
OT10	0.9602	64252.01	14334.53
OT2	0.9931	63898.62	14442.88
E6M	4.3865	118847.26	49324.34
CRED	1.4517	33619.81	15338.12
TXCRED	7.7632	164785.90	81484.75

Note: Highlighted values represent the 3 lowest MAPE, RMSE, and MAD values for the hybrid models.

As seen in the literature (Martins et al., 2021) wages are a valid approach to determine 474
income elasticity of the electricity demand. (Martins et al., 2021) indicates that wages 475
elasticity is around 0.3 on the short and long-run for electricity demand in Brazil between 476
2004 and 2019. Nevertheless, the break down per regions inspection determined a wide 477
range of elasticities, between 0.1 and 1. Figure 7 shows that NLV1 consumption was 478
not affected by COVID-19 and clearly has a very seasonal pattern with strong increases 479
during the winter. 480

Figure 7: Actual and forecast electricity demand for NLV1 using wages

NLV2

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For NLV2 the installed capacity is between 13,8 kV and 20,7 kV. According to the SARIMAX model for an increase of 1% in the economic sentiment index (Table 11) there is an increase on the electricity demand of 0.0969% (Additionally, the standard error is 0.1916). On the SARIMAX model, economic sentiment index is not significant at a 5% level.

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Table 11: Performance Metrics for Hybrid Models

Variable	MAPE (%)	RMSE (MWh)	MAD (MWh)
GDP	0.3579	4151.63	750.21
INV	0.9884	4711.98	1736.94
PC	0.5069	5795.25	1054.67
IEB	0.2240	1200.85	401.62
NFA	3.2844	14873.27	6942.52
FDI	1.1199	5699.27	1969.28
ER	1.5283	7845.39	2620.01
UR	0.8561	4552.47	1451.02
IPI	1.9234	9685.21	4084.23
ESI	0.0959	383.75	179.26
CCI	0.8307	6563.72	1800.99
ICI	0.4426	2975.72	930.61
PS	0.4037	4400.95	846.36
PAI	0.7083	3903.21	1163.62
W	1.8953	9401.50	3990.92
PD	21.4102	50208.53	42916.48
PSI20	1.5505	7565.82	2522.57
ESTXX	1.2876	7241.47	2292.86
OT10	0.6882	4230.93	1092.23
OT2	0.9825	6029.08	1545.09
E6M	14.4775	44712.04	28360.89
CRED	1.2719	6584.17	2163.83
TXCRED	0.8339	4288.25	1379.01

Note: Highlighted values represent the 3 lowest MAPE, RMSE, and MAD values for the hybrid models.

In this segment, the economic sentiment index emerges as the key indicator. Nevertheless, variables such as GDP and private consumption also demonstrate high predictive accuracy. This suggests that the main drivers of electricity consumption may include both the general economic sentiment and the actual economic output.

Figure 8 a slight rebound effect of electricity consumption after the COVID-19 years, yet still short of the maximum values observed in 2012 and 2013.

Figure 8: Actual and forecast electricity demand for NLV2 using ESI

Now, it is analyzed the segment of consumers with the lowest capacity installed. They represent above 90% of the number of active contracts, but due to its less intensive nature (domestic tasks, low levels of income) they only have around 35% to 40% of total electricity consumption.

On this voltage segment the SARIMAX model indicates that for an increase of 1% in the loan interest rate (Table 12) there is an increase on the electricity demand of 0.0568% (Additionally, the standard error is 0.0175). On the SARIMAX model, non financial corporations interest rate is significant at a 5% level.

Table 12: Performance Metrics for Hybrid and ARIMA Models

Variable	MAPE (%)	RMSE (MWh)	MAD (MWh)
GDP	2.1035	10605.38	2309.92
INV	2.6331	10804.13	3046.61
PC	2.0500	9864.85	2293.35
IEB	2.8893	10329.89	3592.82
NFA	2.5537	10466.73	3106.22
FDI	3.3796	10435.06	4386.23
ER	3.0998	10961.57	3885.72
UR	2.4014	10178.91	2844.63
IPI	3.7899	11257.18	4935.35
ESI	3.5856	10943.24	4799.86
CCI	2.6995	9884.96	3211.37
ICI	2.3161	9616.21	2556.04
PS	2.2152	10069.51	2550.43
PAI	2.6281	11229.44	2976.21
W	3.7890	11456.46	5115.67
PD	19.3047	41288.44	30532.31
PSI20	3.6222	11222.13	4821.02
ESTXX	4.6892	13110.95	6172.70
OT10	2.8188	10588.58	3305.01
OT2	2.4837	10143.26	2695.52
E6M	7.3048	24036.07	10539.47
CRED	3.1633	11494.13	3789.92
TXCRED	1.9779	9476.42	2198.41

Note: Highlighted values represent the 3 lowest MAPE, RMSE, and MAD values for hybrid models only.

As observed in the higher voltages levels, this segment also has credit conditions as the key predictor. Nevertheless with a small difference: Regarding VHV the variable was linked with treasury bonds as for the NLV3 the interest rate is associated with private commercial lending.

Figure 9 shows that at times during COVID-19, electricity consumption had large decreases that influenced the forecasting accuracy.

Figure 9: Actual and forecast electricity demand for NLV3 using TXCRED

PI

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Public illumination are the technologies systems that provide artificial light to outdoor public spaces and it is a key part of urban infrastructure. 509
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In the SARIMAX model an increase of 1% in the eurostoxx index price (Table 8) there is an increase on the electricity demand of 0.4005% (Additionally, the standard error is 0.0908). On the SARIMAX model, the eurostoxx market index is significant at a 5% level. 511
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Table 13: Performance Metrics for Forecasting Models

Variable	MAPE (%)	RMSE (MWh)	MAD (MWh)
GDP	9.8115	12166.45	6459.06
INV	5.3453	8168.88	3528.76
PC	8.4810	11121.14	5604.63
IEB	1.4482	2898.57	948.71
NFA	5.5652	8373.55	3668.73
FDI	3.2136	5803.75	2103.22
ER	2.9934	5505.77	1959.57
UR	3.2761	5720.34	2132.06
IPI	5.8812	8701.91	3876.19
ESI	5.1053	7926.52	3369.60
CCI	5.6109	8389.24	3693.86
ICI	5.1569	7947.06	3391.67
PS	5.1936	8024.35	3452.45
PAI	8.9296	11508.14	6019.64
W	5.5177	8300.53	3641.67
PD	0.0708	64.93	55.22
PSI20	5.2565	8078.31	3452.70
ESTXX	0.0581	53.28	textbf44.53
OT10	0.4571	1380.82	textbf282.98
OT2	0.4291	1191.28	textbf271.80
E6M	17.0801	18779.92	11204.74
CRED	2.0915	4228.72	1365.84
TXCRED	3.2659	4785.64	1997.14

Note: Values represent the performance metrics for the forecasting models.

There is little justification that can support the impact of the European market index 515
on the public illumination. Nevertheless, it is interesting to note that the second closest 516
MAPE is public debt, which can show a significant relationship between lighting costs 517
and public budget. 518

Figure 10 shows the comparison between actual and forecasted values. It should be 519
noted that the declining is mainly due to energy efficiency measures, namely the switch 520
to LED that it is not counterbalanced by the rebound effect. 521

Figure 10: Actual and forecast electricity demand for PI using ESTXX

Total

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For the total consumption the SARIMAX model points to an increase of 1% in the economic activity (Table 14) leads to an increase on the electricity demand of 0.5098% (Additionally, the standard error is 0.0783). On the SARIMAX model, the economic growth is significant at a 5% level.

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Table 14: Performance Metrics for Corrected and ARIMA Models

Variable	MAPE (%)	RMSE (MWh)	MAD (MWh)
GDP	0.272	58288.18	11012.49
INV	4.426	353589.08	166405.34
PC	0.827	112707.01	32864.47
IEB	0.860	124248.77	33770.46
NFA	2.911	260556.83	110191.34
IDE	2.166	217703.51	82816.53
ER	2.210	219685.01	84599.10
UR	1.562	186299.86	60729.17
IPI	0.298	37986.40	11885.26
ESI	1.264	170461.61	49805.09
CCI	2.587	243440.33	98207.41
ICI	1.555	187648.53	60720.63
PS	2.529	218179.28	96097.61
PAI	1.419	170292.57	56281.54
W	1.240	162181.94	47809.40
PD	20.661	945972.17	775242.95
PSI20	1.270	163142.66	49554.31
ESTXX	2.588	249534.74	97226.17
OT10	1.154	155017.23	45085.35
OT2	3.264	284958.42	123312.51
E6M	0.275	44080.90	10980.26
CRED	1.986	207482.08	75656.24
TXCRED	0.610	90292.53	23895.33

Note: Values represent the performance metrics for the corrected models.

Income elasticity for total demand is well within the interval given in literature (between 0 and slight above 1). It should be noted that the given elasticities by the SARIMAX model are short-run income elasticities that usually are slightly lower than the long-run ones (consumers may have limited flexibility to adjust their electricity usage in response to changes in income. Factors such as long-term investments in energy-efficient technologies, changes in lifestyle, or shifts to alternative energy sources can take time to implement (Hardmeier et al., 2024).

Figure 11: Actual and forecast electricity demand for Total using GDP

Overall the results seem to point to two distinct dynamics: i) for higher levels of voltages (characterized by intensive consumers, usually related to industrial or services that use a lot of power), investment conditions seem rather important for forecasting electricity consumption. But, for ii) lower voltage levels results are mixed: economic activity, wages, credit conditions and index stock markets provide insightful information. Lastly, it is provided a wide range of macroeconomic variables that perform well. Following closely the forecasts of the national and international institutions can provide valuable information for predicting the electricity consumption per voltage level. It is important to notice that these projections will yield less reliable forecasts as there will be, certainly, deviations from the actual values.

5. Conclusions

In this paper we analyzed the best macroeconomic predictors for monthly portuguese electricity consumption between 2012 and 2023 per voltage level. The methodological approach consisted on the determination of a hybrid model SARIMAX + SVR that would yield the best accuracy while systematically rotating the macroeconomic variable under consideration.

The findings indicate that for high voltage systems, which primarily serve industrial users, investment conditions (related to industrial production OT2, IEB, FDI) are the most significant predictors of electricity demand. These results reinforce the strong link between industrial activity and energy consumption (Liddle and Hasanov, 2022), emphasizing the need for forecasts that account for fluctuations in industrial performance. In contrast, for low voltage systems, serving residential and small commercial users, a mix of macroeconomic variables related to economic activity, household income, or credit interest rates were the selected variables. This underscores the sensitivity of residential electricity

demand to a set of macroeconomic variables, suggesting, for example, that policies aimed at enhancing household income could directly influence residential energy consumption patterns.

Based on these findings, policymakers and utilities should consider developing differentiated forecasting models that account for the specific characteristics of low and high voltage systems. By recognizing the distinct macroeconomic drivers for industrial and residential sectors, these models can provide more accurate demand predictions, aiding in more efficient energy system planning. Furthermore, the significant role of macroeconomic variables like industrial output, household income, and wages in determining electricity demand suggests that energy policies should be closely aligned with broader economic trends. For example, policies promoting industrial growth could be complemented with infrastructure investments in high voltage systems, while measures to improve energy efficiency in public illumination might be reflected in adjustments to investment in network that supplies it.

Utilities should also prioritize investments in network capacity and infrastructure based on the identified macroeconomic drivers. Understanding the sensitivity of residential demand to household income and wages, for instance, could guide investments in low voltage distribution networks to ensure reliable service in light of expected income fluctuations. Additionally, tariff structures should be designed with consideration for the differing impacts of macroeconomic variables on residential and industrial demand (according to [Schittekatte et al., 2018](#)) energy will remain a driver for the tariff structure). For residential consumers, income-sensitive pricing models that account for wage changes could ensure affordability during economic downturns, while for industrial users, dynamic tariffs reflecting industrial production trends could help manage demand spikes.

Finally, coordination between energy planners, economic policymakers, and industry stakeholders is essential to ensure that energy system investments and policies align with macroeconomic developments. Regular updates to demand forecasting models incorporating the latest economic data can improve the responsiveness of energy systems to changing market conditions. In summary, this paper contributes valuable insights into the complex relationship between macroeconomic factors and electricity demand. By incorporating these insights into energy planning and policy, utilities and policymakers can enhance the efficiency and resilience of energy systems, ensuring that they are well-equipped to meet the evolving needs of different consumer segments and to respond to a quickly transformation that have been arising in the energy markets.

In order to further developed this research, some improvements can be added upon: i) Increase the size of the sample or conduct the study using a panel data framework; ii) Incorporate effects that may further explain the behaviour of electricity consumption, in particular, regarding energy transition variables like energy efficiency, self-consumption or electrification; iii) robust checks with other methodologies, for example, Lasso, Ridge or Net Elasticity regressions; iv) use of other temporal disaggregation techniques; v) combine

several macroeconomic variables. 598

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